

THE CONCEPT OF “SUBTITLES” AND THEIR WORKING IN THE TEXT

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Annotation. *The film industry and everything connected with it invariably arouses interest and controversy among specialists in various fields, as well as among ordinary spectators. In recent decades, due to the active development of the field communications, the Internet and various social networks, interest in film production increased several times. And since the main films are released in English, interest has grown in such a phenomenon as subtitles for movies and series.*

Key words: *film industry, frame, subtitle, caption, language, film, broadcast time, characters, comments.*

In order to define such a term as "subtitle", first turn, it is necessary to consider well-known concepts, thanks to which it becomes clear that the "subtitle" includes two morphemes: prefixes "sub" (from the Latin sub - "location below something, or near something"), and the root "caption" (from the French titre - "introductory inscription or explanatory text in the movie).

Subtitle - an inscription located at the bottom of the frame. Text a subtitle is usually a translation into another language of the words of the actor (announcer) or inscriptions. Films for the deaf are also subtitled. [6].

According to the "Big Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language", the term subtitle means "the caption under the image inside the frame, conveying words of actors or containing explanatory text.

It is interesting to note that in the traditional source ("Dictionary linguistic terms, ed. Akhmanova O. S.) this term does not exist. The absence of the term "subtitle" in specialized linguistic dictionaries is a kind of confirmation that subtitles for various

television and film materials were not considered for a long time in linguistic aspect, but rather were considered a cinematic reality.

Thus, selecting and summarizing information from all of the above definitions, we agree to divide the subtitles into two type of text that characterizes their use. These are subtitles reproducing the speech of characters in the original language (usually they accompany films for the deaf), as well as subtitles representing is a translation of the original text of the film into a language understandable viewer.

When defining such a thing as a "subtitle", within the framework of this work, this term will be considered solely as a text, which is a translation of the original film text into the language understandable to the viewer, in our case, we consider the English-Russian language pair.

Based on the work of Egorova T. A., all subtitles can be combined into relevant groups. As a rule, the classification is carried out according to seven basic grounds [9].

1. If possible, turn on and off:

- hidden (you can turn it on and off);
- open (i.e. displayed on the screen, they cannot be turned off).

2. According to the form in which they are stored:

- sewn (image and text are superimposed on the original video sequence);
- pre-rendered (originally finished material, stored separately from the video sequence, this is how DVD-video subtitles are stored);
- programmatic (text, often with markup elements, i.e. font, color, position on the screen, etc.).

3. According to the language of presentation, subtitles can be:

- original;
- transferable.

4. By broadcast time, subtitles are divided into the following types:

- coming out in real time;
- compiled in advance;

- part is prepared in advance, and part is released in the mode real time.

5. According to the level of detail of events, subtitles are divided into:

- containing only replicas of characters and comments to inscriptions in the frame;
- containing additional, informative or explanatory information.

6. According to the content, subtitles can be:

- narrative;
- forced (containing translation);
- extended (combination of localized and standard subtitles);
- localized (containing an explanation for the element, located in the text of the subtitles);
- informative (containing explanatory information to what is happening in the frame);
- bonus (separate subtitles related to voice-over information and photography).

7. According to the scope of use, the following types of subtitles are distinguished:

- artistic (used in movies, opera, theatrical performances);
- media subtitles (used in news, advertising);
- entertaining (used in videos, computer games that teach the language of programs) [4].

The above classification of subtitles allows us to compose a general idea of them as a whole. Consider one of the areas of use of subtitles, in this case film discourse.

Based on the article by M. A. Samkova devoted to the issue correlation between the concepts of "film text" and "film discourse", it can be argued that the concept of film discourse can be defined through the concept of film text.

Cinematic text in relation to film discourse can be considered as its fragment, but film discourse as a whole text or a set of combined some sign of the texts.

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